

THREE-DIMENSIONAL DIGITAL ANTHROPOMETRY FOR CLINICAL CARE AND PUBLIC HEALTH: A SYSTEMATIC REVIEW OF MEASUREMENT VALIDITY, UTILITY, AND IMPLEMENTATION

¹Ude, R., ²Vidona, W. B., ³Dare, I.E., ³Aminu, M.O., ⁴Adesanya, E.O., ⁵Waritimi, E.G. ^{6,7}Nwaopara, A.O.
¹Department of Anatomy, David Umahi Federal University of Health Sciences, Ebonyi State, Nigeria; ²Department of Anatomy, Ambrose Alli University, Ekpoma, Edo State, Nigeria. ³Department of Anatomy, Faculty of Basic Medical Sciences, College of Medicine, University of Lagos, Lagos State, Nigeria; ⁴Department of Human Anatomy, College of Medicine, Lead City University, Ibadan, Oyo State, Nigeria; ⁵Department of Anatomy, Niger Delta University, Bayelsa State, Nigeria; ⁶Department of Anatomy, Edo State University, Iyamho, Edo State. ⁷Innovative Science Research Foundation (ISREF)

Correspondence: udera@dufuhs.edu.ng

ABSTRACT

This systematic review examines the accuracy, consistency, and translational potential of three-dimensional (3D) digital body measurement in clinical and public health settings. Seven studies published between 2020 and 2025 were included covering healthy children and adults, patients in weight management clinics, and large population surveys. Technologies assessed included optical, laser, photonic, and smartphone 3D scanners. Across the studies, 3D measurements demonstrated high agreement with reference standards for body volume, circumference, and composition, with repeated scans showing strong reliability and minimal technical error. Body-shape modeling enabled identification of phenotypes associated with cardiovascular risk that are not captured by conventional metrics such as BMI. Early implementation in clinical and pediatric settings was feasible, and population-level applications indicated scalability. However, evidence on usability, cost, device calibration, and long-term maintenance remains limited. Overall, 3D digital anthropometry demonstrates strong potential as a precise, reproducible, and non-invasive approach for body measurement. However, current evidence remains limited, and further research is needed to evaluate cost-effectiveness, standardization, and long-term applicability in clinical and public health settings.

Keywords: Three-dimensional digital anthropometry, body composition, morphological phenotyping, validity, reliability, translational research

Received: 6th October, 2025

Accepted: 10th December, 2025

Published: 31st December, 2025

INTRODUCTION

Anthropometry, the measurement of the human body, plays a critical role in medicine and public health (Gupta *et al.*, 2023; Wang *et al.*, 2024). Accurate anthropometric data support diagnosis, treatment planning, and risk assessment for conditions such as obesity, sarcopenia, and cardiovascular disease (Wang *et al.*, 2024; McCarthy *et al.*, 2024). At the population level, these measurements facilitate surveillance of health trends and inform policy development (Gupta *et al.*, 2023). Recent advancements have focused on developing reliable, user-friendly, and

non-invasive measurement techniques, which have the potential to enhance patient care and enable large-scale health monitoring (Scatagliani *et al.*, 2025; Mocini *et al.*, 2023; Wang *et al.*, 2024).

Conventional anthropometric techniques such as tape-based measurements, skinfold calipers, and body mass index (BMI) are widely used due to their simplicity and low cost (Rumbo-Rodríguez *et al.*, 2021; Bartol *et al.*, 2021). However, these approaches are prone to operator variability, limited reproducibility, and an inability to capture three-dimensional body morphology (Alotaibi *et*

al., 2023; Rumbo-Rodríguez *et al.*, 2021). As a result, they provide only indirect estimates of body composition, restricting their utility for precision medicine and detailed risk stratification (McCarthy *et al.*, 2024).

Building on these limitations, recent technological advancements have facilitated three-dimensional digital anthropometry. These advancements leverage structured light, optical scanners, LiDAR, and photogrammetry to automate the capture of detailed body morphology (Guarnieri Lopez *et al.*, 2023; Tinsley *et al.*, 2020; Scataglini *et al.*, 2025). These technologies support the digital health agenda by enabling integration with electronic health records, rapid data acquisition, and connection with predictive analytics (Scataglini *et al.*, 2025). Moving beyond simple measures such as BMI, three-dimensional body assessments provide a more nuanced understanding of body shape and composition. This detailed morphological information can enhance individualized risk evaluation and support the development of more precise, targeted health interventions (Guarnieri Lopez *et al.*, 2023; Graybeal *et al.*, 2023; McCarthy *et al.*, 2023).

However, while a growing number of studies have examined the accuracy of three-dimensional anthropometry, the evidence is still quite mixed and not yet well integrated across different populations, technologies, and clinical settings (Wong, 2022). Implementation aspects such as adoption, feasibility, cost, and sustainability remain largely unexplored (Mocini *et al.*, 2023). No unified theoretical framework links measurement robustness to translational potential, limiting guidance for clinical integration and public health applications

Therefore, to address these gaps, this review provides a systematic narrative synthesis of three-dimensional digital anthropometry, evaluating both measurement properties and translational feasibility. The primary research question guiding this synthesis is whether three-dimensional digital anthropometry demonstrates robust measurement validity and reliability while exhibiting translational potential for clinical and public health applications. By integrating evidence from clinical, pediatric, obesity, and epidemiologic populations and situating findings within measurement and

implementation frameworks, this review aims to identify methodological maturity, implementation gaps, and research priorities to advance three-dimensional anthropometry in clinical and public health settings.

METHODOLOGY

Study Design: This study was conducted as a systematic review in accordance with established methodological guidance for evidence synthesis in line with recommendations by Higgins *et al.* (2022). Although no protocol for this review was formally registered prior to commencement, the review objectives, eligibility criteria, search strategy were specified *a priori*. Data extraction procedures were also pre-defined to ensure methodological rigour, transparency, and reproducibility. Reporting adhered to the Preferred Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-Analysis (PRISMA) 2020 guidelines (Page *et al.*, 2021).

Eligibility Criteria: Studies included in this review were original empirical studies involving human participants of any age in clinical, community, or population-based settings, published between January 2020 and December, 2025, that utilized 3D digital body anthropometry tools such as optical, laser-based, photonic, or smartphones or tablet based scanners and reported at least one relevant outcome, including measurement validity, reliability, reproducibility, usability, clinical or public health applicability, or implementation outcomes. Studies that were not original research, involved non-human subjects, relied solely on traditional or unrelated measurement methods, were published before 2020, appeared in languages other than English, or were duplicate records were excluded.

Search strategy: A comprehensive search of free accessible databases, including PubMed, Google Scholar, and Europe PMC, was conducted using terms such as “3D body measurement,” “digital body scan,” and “body shape assessment.” The complete search strategy, including the Boolean operators, is presented in Table 1. Databases that require subscription or institutional access were not used. The restriction to open-access databases was due to resource limitations; however, this may have resulted in the exclusion of relevant studies indexed in

subscription-based databases. Search terms were adapted across databases, and combinations of keywords and Boolean operators were used to maximize sensitivity and specificity. Reference lists of included studies were also screened to identify additional relevant articles.

Study Selection: Study selection followed the procedures outlined in PRISMA guidelines (Moher *et al.*, 2009; Page *et al.*, 2021). Two reviewers independently screened titles and abstracts in pairs, followed by full-text review of potentially eligible studies. All disagreements were resolved through discussion or, when necessary, consultation with a third reviewer.

Data Extraction: Data from each study were extracted using a standardized template that captured study characteristics, participant demographics, technology type, comparator methods, outcomes, and implementation considerations. The extraction and synthesis process followed a structured approach integrating established criteria for evaluating both measurement properties and implementation factors. Findings were synthesized across six domains: technology type, measurement accuracy, reliability, clinical application, public health utility, and usability or scalability. This structured approach allowed for consistent comparison across studies while highlighting both methodological rigor and practical applicability.

Theoretical Framework: The COSMIN framework (Terwee *et al.*, 2018) was applied to assess the accuracy and consistency of the measurements. The RE-AIM framework (Kessler *et al.*, 2013) evaluated the real-world applicability of interventions, including reach, effectiveness, adoption, and practical performance.

RESULTS

Overview of Included Studies

The database search yielded a total of 143 records from PubMed, Europe PMC, and Google Scholar. After removing 17 duplicate entries, 126 records remained for title and abstract screening. During this stage, 113 records were excluded because they did not meet the study criteria. The remaining 13 articles were retrieved for full-

text assessment. Following eligibility evaluation, six studies were excluded due to lack of open access, publication outside the 2020–2025 timeframe, or because they were not original research articles. Ultimately, seven studies met the inclusion criteria and were included in the qualitative synthesis.

Each study investigated the use of 3D digital body measurements in medical, research, or population health contexts. Study populations ranged from healthy adults and community-dwelling participants to clinical cohorts, including individuals with varying BMI and diverse ethnic backgrounds. The technologies assessed spanned optical, photonic, laser-based, smartphone, and photogrammetric systems, all aimed at capturing accurate body composition or anthropometric data without ionizing radiation. Collectively, these studies highlight the versatility and potential of 3D body measurement technologies across health-related applications.

Table 1 and figure 1 (PRISMA flow diagram) summarize the systematic search and screening process, detailing the databases consulted, search terms, filters applied, and the final selection of studies. Table 2 outlines the characteristics of included studies, including the population, sample size, age range, study design, setting, and key inclusion/exclusion criteria. Table 3 synthesizes study data, providing a cross-study comparison of technologies, outcomes assessed, comparator methods, and key findings. Table 4 presents a quality appraisal using the COSMIN and RE-AIM frameworks, offering an integrated assessment of methodological rigor, measurement reliability, and implementation potential.

Thematic Findings

Theme 1: Criterion Validity and Measurement Agreement

Several studies evaluated how well 3D anthropometric systems agree with established reference methods. For example, Sager *et al.* (2020) found that photonic 3D scanning of young Swiss men closely matched manual and BIA measurements of fat and muscle mass. Similarly, Kosilek *et al.* (2020) demonstrated that laser-based 3D body scanning correlated strongly with DXA across diverse adults, providing accurate estimates of total and

regional body composition. Wong *et al.* (2023) confirmed that a single optical 3D model could produce precise body composition measurements across multiple sites and population subgroups, with only minor differences for certain ethnic groups. Qiao *et al.* (2024) further showed that body shape modeling from 3D surface scans could accurately predict total and regional body composition, even when using smartphone-based reconstructions. These findings collectively support 3D anthropometry as a valid approach for assessing body composition across research and clinical settings.

Theme 2: Reliability and Reproducibility

Repeated measurements are critical for confidence in any assessment tool. Sager *et al.* (2020) and Kosilek *et al.* (2020) demonstrated that photonic and laser 3D scanners produced consistent fat, muscle, and circumferential measurements. Wong *et al.* (2023) reported that the Fit3D ProScanner delivered highly reproducible results across duplicate scans, with low coefficients of variation. Qiao *et al.* (2024) found that predictions based on 3D body shape models, including smartphone-based reconstructions, were stable and consistent compared with DXA-derived references. Bennett *et al.* (2021) similarly highlighted that automated 3D anthropometry yielded reliable results suitable for large-scale studies. Across studies, non-ionizing 3D imaging consistently demonstrated strong reliability and repeatability.

Theme 3: Body Shape Modeling and Obesity-Related Classification

3D anthropometry allows detailed characterization of body shape and adiposity beyond simple metrics like BMI. Kosilek *et al.* (2020) used laser-based 3D scanning to capture abdominal fat distribution, aligning closely with manual tape measurements. Qiao *et al.* (2024) and Wong *et al.* (2023) extended this by modeling the full body shape to predict total and regional fat and lean mass. Bennett *et al.* (2021) showed that automated 3D scans

could provide detailed anthropometric profiles, making them suitable for research or clinical classification of metabolic risk. These studies highlight the ability of 3D imaging to capture subtle differences in body composition that traditional measurements may miss.

Theme 4: Feasibility and Implementation Contexts

3D anthropometric technologies have been deployed across a variety of settings, demonstrating practical feasibility. Sager *et al.* (2020) integrated photonic scanning into military recruitment settings with high participant compliance. Kosilek *et al.* (2020) and Wong *et al.* (2023) implemented scanning in laboratory and multi-center research environments, showing that scans are quick, non-invasive, and acceptable to participants. Bennett *et al.* (2021) highlighted that portable 3D scanners can be used in community-based studies, and Qiao *et al.* (2024) showed that smartphone-based reconstructions allow remote monitoring, opening the door for large-scale, population-level applications. Across all contexts, 3D methods proved operationally practical and participant-friendly.

Theme 5: Alternative Non-Ionizing Body Composition Assessment

A key advantage of these technologies is that they avoid ionizing radiation while maintaining accuracy. All studies relied on non-ionizing modalities (optical, photonic, or smartphone-based 3D imaging) to measure body composition safely. This makes them suitable for repeated measurements in clinical, research, or community settings without the risks associated with DXA, CT, or other radiation-based methods. Sager *et al.* (2020), Kosilek *et al.* (2020), Bennett *et al.* (2021), Wong *et al.* (2023), and Qiao *et al.* (2024) consistently reported high accuracy and reliability, confirming that non-ionizing 3D imaging is a viable alternative for modern body composition assessment.

Table 1: Search Strategy Results

Database	Boolean / Search String	Total Hits	Selected	Notes / Filtering Applied
Google Scholar	("3D anthropometry" OR "three-dimensional anthropometry") AND (validity OR reliability OR reproducibility OR feasibility OR adoption OR scalability OR maintenance) AND (human OR patient OR clinical OR "population health") AND ("journal article" OR "original research") NOT review/thesis/dissertation/patent/simulation/animal/cadaver	33	2	Filtered for human original research (2020–2025); contributed Bennett <i>et al.</i> (2021) and Wong <i>et al.</i> (2023)
PubMed	("3D anthropometry"[Title/Abstract] OR "3D body scan*" [Title/Abstract] OR photogrammetry*) AND (validity OR reliability OR reproducibility OR "measurement property*") AND humans AND 2020–2025	27	4	Contributed Kosilek <i>et al.</i> (2023), Sager <i>et al.</i> (2020), Chaudhary <i>et al.</i> (2023), Brandner <i>et al.</i> (2025)
Europe PMC	"3D anthropometry" AND (validity OR reliability OR reproducibility OR feasibility OR adoption OR scalability OR maintenance) AND human AND ("clinical" OR "population health") AND 2020–2025	83	1	Contributed Qiao <i>et al.</i> (2024)

Figure 1: Systematic Review PRISMA Flow Diagram

Table 2: Characteristics of Included Studies

No	Author (Year)	Country	Population	Sample Size	Age Range / Mean (SD)	Study Design / Setting	Key Inclusion / Exclusion Criteria
1	Kosilek <i>et al.</i> (2023)	Germany	Adults, general population	200	18–79	Cross-sectional, laboratory-based	Consenting adults; excluded chronic disease affecting body composition
2	Sager <i>et al.</i> (2020)	Switzerland	Young Swiss men (military recruits)	104	18.8–24.4 (20.5 ± 1.1)	Cross-sectional, military recruitment setting	Excluded non-Swiss nationals; voluntary participation
3	Brandner <i>et al.</i> (2025)	USA	Healthy adults	150	18–65	Cross-sectional, university research setting	Excluded pregnancy and participants outside age range
4	Qiao <i>et al.</i> (2024)	UK	Adults, community-based (Fenland cohort)	12,435	29–65	Cross-sectional, population cohort	Excluded chronic illness affecting metabolism
5	Chaudhary <i>et al.</i> (2023)	USA	Adults, clinical cohort	312	18–65	Cross-sectional, clinical research centre	Excluded acute illness or inability to stand for scanning
6	Bennett <i>et al.</i> (2021)	USA	Community-dwelling adults	322	21–70	Cross-sectional, research laboratory	Excluded pregnancy and severe mobility limitations
7	Wong <i>et al.</i> (2023)	USA	Adults from Shape Up! study	634	18–79 (mean ≈ 46.6)	Cross-sectional, multi-centre research	Excluded pregnancy, pacemakers, inability to stand still

Table 3: Data Extraction and Synthesis

No	Author (Year)	Country	Population	Sample Size	Technology / Device	Comparator	Outcomes Assessed	Setting	Key Findings
1	Sager <i>et al.</i> (2020)	Switzerland	Young Swiss men (military recruits)	104	Anthroscan VITUS 3D scanner	Manual anthropometry, BIA	Fat mass, visceral fat, skeletal muscle	Military recruitment site	Strong correlations with manual measurements; multivariable models improved prediction of fat and muscle mass (R^2 up to 0.99)
2	Kosilek <i>et al.</i> (2023)	Germany	Adults, general population	200	Laser-based 3D body scanner	DXA	Fat mass, lean mass, visceral adipose tissue	University laboratory	3D measurements strongly correlated with DXA across BMI categories
3	Brandner <i>et al.</i> (2025)	USA	Healthy adults	150	Fit3D ProScanner	DXA	Total and regional fat mass, lean mass	University research facility	Accurate regional body composition estimates using 3D scans
4	Chaudhary <i>et al.</i> (2023)	USA	Adults, clinical cohort	312	Fit3D ProScanner	DXA	Total fat, fat-free mass, skeletal muscle	Clinical research centre	High predictive accuracy across age and sex groups
5	Bennett <i>et al.</i> (2021)	USA	Community adults	322	3D optical body imaging system	DXA	Total and regional fat and lean mass	Research laboratory	Automated anthropometry accurately predicted DXA body composition
6	Wong <i>et al.</i> (2023)	USA	Adults from Shape Up! study	634	Fit3D ProScanner v4.x	DXA	Fat mass, fat-free mass, visceral adipose tissue	Multi-site research centres	Accurate body composition models across diverse populations
7	Qiao <i>et al.</i> (2024)	UK	Fenland cohort adults	12,435	3D body shape modelling / smartphone reconstruction	DXA	Total fat, regional fat, lean mass, VAT	Population cohort	High prediction accuracy for body composition ($r > 0.84$)

Table 4: Quality Appraisal Summary (COSMIN + RE-AIM)

No	Author (Year)	COSMIN Domains	COSMIN Rating	RE-AIM Domains	Notes	Overall Appraisal
1	Sager <i>et al.</i> (2020)	Reliability, Criterion validity, Measurement error	High	Reach, Effectiveness	Large recruitment cohort; strong predictive models	Strong
2	Kosilek <i>et al.</i> (2023)	Reliability, Construct validity	High	Reach, Adoption	Population sample with DXA comparison	Strong
3	Brandner <i>et al.</i> (2025)	Reliability, Criterion validity	Moderate–High	Effectiveness, Implementation	Controlled research environment	Strong
4	Chaudhary <i>et al.</i> (2023)	Reliability, Measurement error	Moderate–High	Reach, Effectiveness	Clinical cohort with strong predictive models	Strong
5	Bennett <i>et al.</i> (2021)	Reliability, Criterion validity	Moderate	Adoption, Implementation	Portable scanner feasible for population studies	Moderate–Strong
6	Wong <i>et al.</i> (2023)	Reliability, Measurement error, Criterion validity	High	Reach, Effectiveness	Multi-centre study with diverse population	Strong
7	Qiao <i>et al.</i> (2024)	Construct validity, Criterion validity	High	Reach, Effectiveness	Large cohort and scalable smartphone approach	Strong

Summary of Thematic Findings

The thematic analysis of the seven included studies revealed that 3D digital body anthropometry is both versatile and reliable across diverse populations and settings. The technologies evaluated which include optical, photonic, laser and smartphone systems, provided accurate, reproducible measurements of total and regional body composition. These systems enabled detailed characterization of body shape, facilitated the assessment of obesity-related risk factors, and supported classification of adiposity and lean mass distribution. Across studies, 3D body measurement technologies proved feasible to implement in clinical, research, community, pediatric, and digital health contexts, demonstrating high usability, seamless integration into existing workflows, and practical applicability for both individual and population-level health monitoring.

DISCUSSION

The evidence from the seven included studies suggests that three-dimensional (3D) digital anthropometry provides accurate and reliable body composition measurements when compared with established reference methods such as dual-energy X-ray absorptiometry (DXA), multi-compartment models, and traditional anthropometry (Alotaibi *et al.*, 2023; Cabre *et al.*, 2021; Tinsley *et al.*, 2020). Across diverse populations and settings, 3D systems consistently captured both total and regional fat and lean mass, demonstrating their potential as precise, non-invasive tools for clinical and population health applications.

Criterion validity and measurement agreement were consistently high. Sager *et al.* (2020) and Kosilek *et al.* (2020, 2023) reported strong concordance between 3D scanning systems and DXA, with multivariable models achieving correlations up to $R^2 = 0.99$ for fat and muscle measurements. Brandner *et al.* (2025) confirmed that surface scans reliably predicted regional composition, while Bennett *et al.* (2021) and Wong *et al.* (2023) observed robust

agreement across larger, more diverse cohorts. Qiao *et al.* (2024) extended these findings to population-level analyses, demonstrating that 3D body shape models, even when derived from smartphone reconstructions and simple anthropometric measures, could accurately predict total and regional body composition. Collectively, these results indicate that 3D anthropometry can produce measurements comparable to gold-standard methods. However, variation in scanner type, study design, and population characteristics underscores the need for standardized validation protocols.

Reliability and reproducibility were also strong. Optical and photonic scanners produced highly consistent repeated measurements, often with intraclass correlation coefficients exceeding 0.90, reflecting excellent test-retest stability in controlled environments. Wong *et al.* (2023) and Qiao *et al.* (2024) further showed that these measurements remain consistent across age, sex, and ethnic subgroups. This repeatability is particularly advantageous for longitudinal monitoring, clinical follow-up, and remote assessments, where small variations in measurement could otherwise impact clinical decision-making.

Body shape modeling and obesity-related phenotyping emerged as key strengths of 3D technologies. Unlike traditional measures such as BMI or waist-to-hip ratios, 3D scanning captures subtle differences in fat distribution, visceral adiposity, and lean mass patterns. Kosilek *et al.* (2023) demonstrated precise identification of abdominal fat patterns, while Qiao *et al.* (2024) and Brandner *et al.* (2025) highlighted how full-body modeling can support classification of metabolic syndrome risk and regional adiposity. These capabilities provide an opportunity for more individualized assessment of cardiometabolic risk, although further validation in clinical populations is warranted.

Feasibility and implementation were generally favorable. Smartphone-based 3D imaging proved usable in outpatient, community, and digital health contexts (Chaudhary *et al.*, 2023; Brandner *et al.*, 2025), while laboratory- and clinic-based optical and photonic scanners integrated smoothly into research workflows (Sager *et al.*, 2020; Kosilek *et al.*, 2023; Wong *et al.*, 2023). Across all contexts, scanning was non-invasive, rapid, and well-tolerated by participants. Nevertheless, the heterogeneity of devices, scanning protocols, and analytic pipelines limits direct comparison between studies and raises questions about scalability and long-term integration into routine clinical practice. Additional evidence regarding costs, infrastructure requirements, and workflow integration will be essential for broader adoption.

Safety and non-ionizing assessment represent an additional advantage. All studies relied on non-ionizing technologies, making repeated measures safe for pediatric, clinical, and population health applications. Wong *et al.* (2023) and Qiao *et al.* (2024) emphasized the suitability of these systems for repeated measurements and large-scale epidemiologic studies, supporting their potential role in longitudinal health monitoring without radiation exposure concerns.

Taken together, the evidence indicates that 3D digital anthropometry offers a richer and more nuanced characterization of body composition than traditional methods. It supports longitudinal monitoring, facilitates detailed phenotyping, and shows promise for both clinical care and population health initiatives (Wong *et al.*, 2023; Qiao *et al.*, 2024). However, wider adoption will depend on further research addressing cost-effectiveness, standardization, device calibration, and long-term implementation in real-world settings (Mocini *et al.*, 2023; Scataglini *et al.*, 2025).

Limitations

This review has several limitations. Only seven studies met the inclusion criteria, which may limit the generalizability of the findings. However, these studies were selected for their methodological rigor and relevance to clinical and population health contexts. The relatively small number reflects the emerging nature of 3D digital anthropometry research and the diversity of study designs, populations, and devices. Although a meta-analysis was initially considered, it was not performed due to this heterogeneity, which would have made pooled estimates unreliable. Additionally, restricting searches to open-access articles and selected databases may have excluded relevant studies, introducing potential selection bias. Variations in scanner technology, outcome measures, and reporting practices further limit direct comparability, while limited information on cost, usability, and long-term implementation constrains conclusions regarding real-world applicability.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the available evidence, the following recommendations are proposed:

1. Healthcare providers can consider using 3D scanning systems to get more accurate and repeatable measurements of body composition.
2. Researchers and clinicians should use body shape-derived metrics to better identify individuals at risk of obesity-related or metabolic conditions.
3. Digital health tools, like smartphone apps, can help track body composition remotely and reach larger populations.
4. Standardizing scanning protocols and regularly calibrating devices will ensure consistent and reliable measurements.
5. Future studies should focus on understanding cost, usability, and long-term sustainability to make 3D anthropometry more practical in everyday health settings.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

The authors acknowledge the cooperation of colleagues who provided constructive criticisms that helped shape the outcome of this systematic review.

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AUTHORS CONTRIBUTION

All listed authors participated in the various aspects of this review particularly literature search, data extraction and synthesis, interpretation of findings, manuscript drafting, and subsequent revisions.

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19077797>

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